

Beauty of Magic Squares: 3240-Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 108 - Part 2

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The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=18266>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72 and 108. (for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different orders** — specifically orders 3 through 8 — each contributing a distinct structural layer.*

*The innermost core is a magic square of order 12 formed by different-sum magic squares of order 3. Successive borders of orders 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 18 are then applied; **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In case of order 8, first three are of equal-sums and last three are of different sums. The same is with order 18, i.e., not all are with equal magic sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations:*

The further study of multiple order bordered magic squares of orders 110, 120, 132 and 144 are given in details in the reference list.

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, pandiagonal magic squares, block-wise construction, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{1}$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [17, 18, 19]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [20, 21, 22, 23]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [3].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [3] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [11, 12, 3].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [30].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [32].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [34].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [36].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [38].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [40].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [42].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [44].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [46].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [74, 75, 76, 77, 77, 78, 79].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [25, 31].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [26, 33].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [27, 35].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [28, 37].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [29, 39].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [41].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [43].
- **Eighteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 [45].
- **Twenty Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 [47].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72 and 108. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

- (a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

- (b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

- (a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

- (b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

- (c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

- (a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

- (b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

- (c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

- (a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

- (b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

- (c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

- (d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.
- (e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.
 - (a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 - (b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.
 - (c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .
 - (d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.
 - (e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.
 - (f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

- **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 18**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18.
 - (a) The first is composed of two types of 6 magic squares of order 6. One is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. The second type is a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and a **pandigonal** magic square of order 4 in the upper-left corner. These are considered in four corners with four different directions resulting a beautiful symmetric magic square of order 18.
 - (b) The second is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 18 embedded with four equal sums magic squares of order 8 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle of all four.
 - (c) The third is **cyclic-type** magic square of order 18 composed of four equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×12 embedded with a **single-layer bordered** magic squares of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle,

- (d) The fourth is **triple-layer bordered** magic square of order 18. The external border is composed of different sums magic squares of order 3. The internal part is a magic square of order 12 composed of two equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×12 .
- (e) The fifth is a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of order 18 **bordered** with four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. It is composed two equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×8 and two equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×6 .
- (f) The sixth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of order 18 **bordered** with four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. It is composed four equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×10 embedded with **single-layer** magic square of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.

Below summarises the six construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**
 - Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.
- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**
 - In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have **2-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**
 - In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have **6-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**
 - In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have **18-different types** of magic squares of order 42.
- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**
 - In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have **90-different types** of magic squares of order 56.
- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have **540-different types** of magic squares of order 72.
- **6th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 18**

– In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18. Combining with 540 magic squares of order 72 we have $6 \times 540 = 3240$, i.e., **3240-different types** of magic squares of order 108.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord.90}} = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 5 \times 6 \times 6 = 3240. \tag{2}$$

More details of last border i.e., 7th border of magic squares of order 18 are given in the following subsection.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 108

In order to get bordered magic squares of order 90, we used following six different types of magic squares of order 9:

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA																	2925
6	320	318	324	3	4	302	300	21	306	22	24	39	40	288	282	42	284	2925	
5	319	7	1	322	321	20	35	292	29	294	305	286	285	37	43	41	283	2925	
9	316	17	310	11	312	26	30	293	36	291	299	53	274	47	276	45	280	2925	
323	2	12	311	18	309	28	296	31	290	33	297	48	275	54	273	279	46	2925	
315	10	314	13	308	15	298	289	34	295	32	27	278	49	272	51	287	38	2925	
317	8	307	16	313	14	301	25	304	19	303	23	271	52	277	50	281	44	2925	
194	192	129	198	130	132	176	174	147	180	148	150	266	264	57	270	58	60	2925	
128	143	184	137	186	197	146	161	166	155	168	179	56	71	256	65	258	269	2925	
134	138	185	144	183	191	152	156	167	162	165	173	62	66	257	72	255	263	2925	
136	188	139	182	141	189	154	170	157	164	159	171	64	260	67	254	69	261	2925	
190	181	142	187	140	135	172	163	160	169	158	153	262	253	70	259	68	63	2925	
193	133	196	127	195	131	175	151	178	145	177	149	265	61	268	55	267	59	2925	
209	116	125	202	119	204	230	228	93	234	94	96	89	238	83	240	245	80	2925	
215	110	120	203	126	201	92	107	220	101	222	233	84	239	90	237	243	82	2925	
207	118	206	121	200	123	98	102	221	108	219	227	242	85	236	87	251	74	2925	
117	208	199	124	205	122	100	224	103	218	105	225	235	88	241	86	81	244	2925	
114	212	210	216	112	111	226	217	106	223	104	99	76	75	252	246	78	248	2925	
113	211	115	109	213	214	229	97	232	91	231	95	249	250	73	79	77	247	2925	
1	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	307	292	294	296	298	318	320	322	34	32	30	28	26	8	6	4	2	308	2925
	25	42	36	288	290	277	47	279	41	74	68	256	258	245	79	247	73	300	2925
	23	39	272	270	51	276	52	54	286	71	240	238	83	244	84	86	254	302	2925
	21	40	50	65	262	59	264	275	285	72	82	97	230	91	232	243	253	304	2925
	19	45	56	60	263	66	261	269	280	77	88	92	231	98	229	237	248	306	2925
	15	287	58	266	61	260	63	267	38	255	90	234	93	228	95	235	70	310	2925
	13	282	268	259	64	265	62	57	43	250	236	227	96	233	94	89	75	312	2925
	11	281	271	55	274	49	273	53	44	249	239	87	242	81	241	85	76	314	2925
	1	284	289	37	35	48	278	46	283	252	257	69	67	80	246	78	251	324	2925
	301	138	132	192	194	181	143	183	137	106	100	224	226	213	111	215	105	24	2925
	303	135	176	174	147	180	148	150	190	103	208	206	115	212	116	118	222	22	2925
	305	136	146	161	166	155	168	179	189	104	114	129	198	123	200	211	221	20	2925
	309	141	152	156	167	162	165	173	184	109	120	124	199	130	197	205	216	16	2925
	311	191	154	170	157	164	159	171	134	223	122	202	125	196	127	203	102	14	2925
	313	186	172	163	160	169	158	153	139	218	204	195	128	201	126	121	107	12	2925
	315	185	175	151	178	145	177	149	140	217	207	119	210	113	209	117	108	10	2925
	316	188	193	133	131	144	182	142	187	220	225	101	99	112	214	110	219	9	2925
	17	33	31	29	27	7	5	3	291	293	295	297	299	317	319	321	323	18	2925
2	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
13	1	323	310	311	16	11	317	321	315	3	9	45	41	283	48	282	276	2925	
320	297	25	19	24	20	299	308	307	304	22	5	37	58	262	266	64	288	2925	
6	27	29	295	292	289	32	34	35	294	298	319	52	61	256	69	264	273	2925	
313	23	296	30	33	36	293	291	290	31	302	12	274	60	253	72	265	51	2925	
7	303	300	306	301	305	26	17	18	21	28	318	275	55	259	66	270	50	2925	
316	324	2	15	14	309	314	8	4	10	322	312	287	56	70	255	269	38	2925	
121	212	114	205	115	208	176	174	147	180	148	150	47	263	68	257	62	278	2925	
109	189	135	131	195	216	146	161	166	155	168	179	281	272	65	260	53	44	2925	
124	133	142	183	192	201	152	156	167	162	165	173	285	271	71	254	54	40	2925	
202	132	181	144	193	123	154	170	157	164	159	171	279	268	258	67	57	46	2925	
203	127	184	141	198	122	172	163	160	169	158	153	39	261	63	59	267	286	2925	
215	128	187	138	197	110	175	151	178	145	177	149	49	284	42	277	43	280	2925	
119	191	140	185	134	206	85	83	88	238	239	251	73	245	249	243	75	81	2925	
209	200	137	188	125	116	248	225	97	96	91	92	227	236	235	232	94	77	2925	
213	199	143	182	126	112	78	99	106	217	220	223	222	107	101	104	226	247	2925	
207	196	186	139	129	118	241	95	219	108	105	102	103	218	224	221	230	84	2925	
111	130	190	194	136	214	79	231	228	229	234	233	98	89	90	93	100	246	2925	
117	113	211	120	210	204	244	242	237	87	86	74	252	80	76	82	250	240	2925	
3	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925
274	279	272	247	252	245	85	90	83	67	72	65	13	18	11	283	288	281	2925
273	275	277	246	248	250	84	86	88	66	68	70	12	14	16	282	284	286	2925
278	271	276	251	244	249	89	82	87	71	64	69	17	10	15	287	280	285	2925
58	63	56	99	102	222	101	231	220	135	138	186	137	195	184	265	270	263	2925
57	59	61	230	209	117	111	213	95	129	173	153	147	177	196	264	266	268	2925
62	55	60	91	212	121	204	113	234	127	176	157	168	149	198	269	262	267	2925
4	9	2	233	109	126	199	216	92	197	145	156	169	180	128	319	324	317	2925
3	5	7	228	215	200	125	110	97	140	182	159	166	143	185	318	320	322	2925
8	1	6	104	218	203	122	107	221	191	179	167	158	146	134	323	316	321	2925
292	297	290	93	114	206	119	211	232	183	150	170	155	175	142	31	36	29	2925
291	293	295	96	210	201	124	115	229	132	144	164	161	181	193	30	32	34	2925
296	289	294	225	108	120	205	217	100	189	174	162	163	151	136	35	28	33	2925
301	306	299	227	118	123	202	207	98	192	154	165	160	171	133	22	27	20	2925
300	302	304	219	112	208	214	116	106	194	148	172	178	152	131	21	23	25	2925
305	298	303	105	223	103	224	94	226	141	187	139	188	130	190	26	19	24	2925
40	45	38	76	81	74	238	243	236	256	261	254	310	315	308	49	54	47	2925
39	41	43	75	77	79	237	239	241	255	257	259	309	311	313	48	50	52	2925
44	37	42	80	73	78	242	235	240	260	253	258	314	307	312	53	46	51	2925
4	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925	
	1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925
	324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925
	49	276	247	236	238	240	256	258	90	88	86	84	70	68	66	248	307	18	2925
	275	50	83	102	231	92	229	91	225	232	98	145	181	140	184	242	305	20	2925
	51	274	81	228	218	108	219	110	104	216	97	179	149	176	146	244	304	21	2925
	273	52	79	95	220	114	111	213	212	105	230	142	178	147	183	246	22	303	2925
	272	53	75	224	103	211	214	112	113	222	101	186	175	150	139	250	302	23	2925
	54	271	73	99	109	217	106	215	221	107	226	182	148	177	143	252	24	301	2925
	270	55	65	227	94	233	96	234	100	93	223	141	144	185	180	260	25	300	2925
	56	269	243	168	156	173	153	199	117	209	120	210	118	124	203	82	299	26	2925
	57	268	245	171	161	164	154	125	194	132	195	134	128	192	200	80	27	298	2925
	267	58	249	151	163	162	174	206	196	138	135	189	188	129	119	76	297	28	2925
	59	266	251	158	166	159	167	121	127	187	190	136	137	198	204	74	296	29	2925
	265	60	253	155	160	165	170	202	133	193	130	191	197	131	123	72	30	295	2925
	264	61	254	172	169	152	157	122	208	116	205	115	207	201	126	71	294	31	2925
	262	63	77	89	87	85	69	67	235	237	239	241	255	257	259	78	32	293	2925
	64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925
	62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925
5	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA																2925
1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925
324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925
49	276	71	249	252	66	72	257	74	70	258	256	89	240	230	91	307	18	2925
275	50	260	247	246	80	243	84	77	81	242	65	96	223	102	229	305	20	2925
51	274	250	78	79	245	82	241	248	244	83	75	93	101	224	232	304	21	2925
273	52	69	76	73	259	253	68	251	255	67	254	239	100	225	86	22	303	2925
272	53	131	200	190	129	176	174	147	180	148	150	233	227	98	92	302	23	2925
54	271	189	183	142	136	146	161	166	155	168	179	88	97	228	237	24	301	2925
270	55	192	144	181	133	152	156	167	162	165	173	231	226	99	94	25	300	2925
56	269	130	141	184	195	154	170	157	164	159	171	235	104	221	90	299	26	2925
57	268	132	182	143	193	172	163	160	169	158	153	87	222	103	238	27	298	2925
267	58	197	137	188	128	175	151	178	145	177	149	234	85	95	236	297	28	2925
59	266	126	186	139	199	214	116	113	215	213	108	211	219	107	109	296	29	2925
265	60	134	140	185	191	105	121	124	120	207	117	202	203	206	220	30	295	2925
264	61	198	187	138	127	115	204	201	205	118	208	123	122	119	210	294	31	2925
262	63	196	125	135	194	216	209	212	110	112	217	114	106	218	111	32	293	2925
64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925
62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925
6	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.
 1. The first is composed of two types of 6 magic squares of order 6. One is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. The second type is a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and a **pandigonal** magic square of order 4 in the upper-left corner. These are considered in four corners with four different directions resulting a beautiful symmetric magic square of order 18.
 2. The second is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 18 embedded with four equal sums magic squares of order 8 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle of all four.
 3. The third is **cyclic-type** magic square of order 18 composed of four equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×12 embedded with a **single-layer bordered** magic squares of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle,
 4. The forth is **triple-layer bordered** magic square of order 18. The external boarder is composed of different sums magic squares of order 3. The internal part is a magic square of order 12 composed of two equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×12 .
 5. The fifth is a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of order 18 **bordered** with four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. It is composed two equal sums **single-layer**

bordered magic rectangles of order 6×8 and two equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×6 .

6. The sixth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of order 18 **bordered** with four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. It is composed four equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×10 embedded with **single-layer** magic square of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.

Combing 540 magic squares of order 72 and 6 magic squares of order 18 lead us to 3240 different types of magic squares of order 108. See below few examples in figures:

Above there are only few examples, but there are 3240 magic squares of order 108 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 18. More details are in an excel file attached with the work.

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